

1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions. Part-XXVIII : Selective 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl nitrones to arylidene acetones[†]

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Abstract : Cycloaddition reactions of *C,N*-diaryl nitrones to arylidene acetones proceeded regio- and stereoselectively to give only 3,4-*trans*-4,5-*trans*-2,3,5-triaryl-4-acetyl-isoxazolidines in high yields.

Keywords : Cycloadditions, nitrones, arylidene acetones, XRD.

Introduction

1,3-Dipolar Cycloaddition (1,3-DC) reactions of nitrones to various unsaturated systems have been extensively studied in the past^{1,2}. We have reported several studies on the cycloaddition reactions of *C,N*-diaryl nitrones to various types of dipolarophiles²⁻⁵. However, on going through earlier literature, no instances of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of nitrones with arylidene acetones were found to have been reported. Hence we undertook the present series of studies on the cycloaddition of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl nitrones to arylidene acetones. Aryl substituents were changed both on the nitrone and dipolarophile to study whether the change had any effect on the selectivity of the cycloaddition process. All the reactions exclusively produced the all *trans*-product in fairly high yields. This was in contrast to the results obtained with cinnamic acid esters and amide derivatives, where small amounts of stereo- and occasionally regio-isomers attended the formation of the major all *trans* isomers⁵.

Results and discussion

The reactions carried out are summarized in Scheme 1.

The reactions were carried out in refluxing anhydrous toluene (~120 °C) under argon atmosphere for 10–16 h with 1 : 3 (dipole : dipolarophile) molar ratio of the reac-

tants. The reactions were monitored by TLC and 300 MHz ¹H NMR analysis of aliquots removed from time to time. The reactions were worked up by removal of solvent under reduced pressure in a rotary evaporator (the crude post-reaction mixture was analysed by TLC and ¹H NMR), followed by purification by column chromatography over neutral alumina.

The structures, relative configurations and conformations of the products were determined by spectroscopic methods including two-dimensional NMR experiments, and confirmed by XRD crystallographic analysis. It was found that all the reactions exclusively produced the all *trans* product, viz. the 3,4-*trans*-4,5-*trans*-2,3,5-triaryl-4-acetyl-isoxazolidine. This was confirmed from the ¹H NMR analysis of the crude reaction mixture which showed the formation of only one cycloadduct.

The spectroscopical analysis is exemplified for a typical example, viz. cycloadduct (**3a**). Its IR spectrum (KBr disc) showed a strong intensity band at 1709 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of an unconjugated carbonyl group, and bands characteristic of the nitro group (1345, 1517 cm⁻¹) and 1,4-disubstituted and mono-substituted benzene rings at 825, 749, 692 cm⁻¹. Complete characterisation of structure as well as the regio- and stereochemistry of the cycloadduct as 3,4-*trans*-4,5-*trans*-2-phenyl-3-(4'-

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

- (1)** : R₁ - (a) NO₂; (b) Cl; (c) H
(2) : R₂ - (a) Cl; (b) H
(3) : R₁ R₂
 (a) NO₂ Cl
 (b) Cl H
 (c) H Cl
 (d) NO₂ H
 (e) H H

Scheme 1. Reactions of *C,N*-diarylnitrones with arylidene acetones.

nitrophenyl)-5-(4''-chlorophenyl)-4-acetyl-isoxazolidine (**3a**) was made from its NMR spectra and finally confirmed by XRD studies. Its 300 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum showed doublets at δ 5.50 (*J* 6.6 Hz) and δ 5.12 (*J* 9.0 Hz) respectively. These two doublets could be assigned to H-3 and H-5 of the isoxazolidine ring. Both were coupled to H-4 appearing as a double doublet at δ 3.75 (*J* 6.6, 9.0 Hz). The methyl protons of -COCH₃ appeared as a singlet at δ 2.18. In the ¹³C NMR spectrum, the non-aromatic methines appeared at δ 71.90, δ 74.84 and δ

82.36 corresponding to C-3, C-4 and C-5 respectively of the isoxazolidine ring. The carbonyl carbon appeared at δ 198.84. Complete assignment of NMR signals was done with the help of two-dimensional NMR spectra, viz. ¹H-¹H COSY, HMQC (Heteronuclear Multi Quantum Coherence, one-bond C-H correlations) for all the compounds and HMBC (Heteronuclear Multiple Bond Correlations, i.e. long-range C-H correlations of smaller magnitude for **3a**, **3b** and **3d**). The assignments are collected in Table 1.

Table 1. 300 MHz ^1H NMR and 75.5 MHz ^{13}C NMR assignments of (**3**)

Carbon no.	Chemical shift (δ ppm)	Multiplicity (J , Hz)	Chemical shift (δ ppm)	DEPT-135 $^\circ$ multiplicity	HMBC w.r.t. proton
3	5.50	d, 6.6	71.90	C-H	C-2,6(B), C-1(A)
4	3.75	dd, 6.5, 9.0	74.84	C-H	C-5
5	5.12	d, 9.0	82.36	C-H	C-2,6(C), C-4
-COCH ₃	2.18	s	28.18	-CH ₃	CO
>CO	-	-	198.84	Quaternary	-
A-1	-	-	150.70	Quaternary	-
A-2,6	6.99	ovl *	114.12	=CH	C-3,5(A)
A-3,5	7.28	t-8.0, d-8.6	129.27	=CH	C-1(A)
A-4	6.99	ovl *	122.32	=CH	-
B-1	-	-	149.10	Quaternary	-
B-2,6	7.75	d, 8.7	127.40	=CH	C-4(B)
B-3,5	8.28	d, 8.7	124.48	=CH	C-1(B)
B-4	-	-	147.70	Quaternary	-
C-1	-	-	136.36	Quaternary	Long-range
C-2,6	7.28	overlapped,	127.36	=CH	couplings among
C-3,5	to 7.53	multiplet	129.18	=CH	ring carbons and
C-4	-	-	132.96	Quaternary	protons

*Overlapped signals.

The structure and stereochemistry of **3a** were confirmed by single crystal XRD analysis. Cycloadduct **3a** was recrystallised from petroleum ether-chloroform to obtain single crystals. The X-ray crystallographic study showed an all *trans*-configuration : H-3 and H-4 were *trans*-oriented, and H-4 and H-5 were also *trans*-oriented. The projection is given in Fig. 1a. Diffraction data were recorded on a Bruker Smart Apex II CCD area detector diffractometer operating the Mo K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.212$ Å). Recording was done at 296 $^\circ$ (2) K. The structures were solved by direct methods (SHELXS) and refined using isotropic, then anisotropic thermal factors (SHELXL program). The crystallographic parameters and detailed results are given in the Experimental part (CCDC reference no. 868952). The compound crystallized in the triclinic system with space group P-1 with two molecules per unit cell; the crystal parameters were : a , b , c - 9.922, 11.537, 11.670 Å respectively; α , β , γ - 116.91 $^\circ$, 107.36 $^\circ$, 99.68 $^\circ$ respectively. The packing in the unit cell is shown in Fig. 1b. In the crystalline array, hydrogen-bond formation is observed between an oxygen of the nitro group and the carbonyl oxygen.

The close similarity in the NMR signals of cycloadducts (**3b-e**), taking into due account the changes caused by the

Fig. 1b. Packing of **3a** in the crystal.

aromatic substituents, confirmed that these also had the same structure and stereochemistry as **3a**. These products arose from an *endo*-carbonyl approach of the dipolarophile, as in the case of the major products obtained from the cycloadditions of the α,β -unsaturated ester and amide dipolarophiles⁵.

Experimental

General :

Melting points were recorded on an electrically heated Köfeler Block apparatus and are uncorrected. Column and thin layer chromatography were carried out using neutral alumina (Qualigens, India), silica gel (Spectrochem, India 60–120 and 100–200 mesh) and silica gel G (Merck, India) respectively. Spots on TLC chromatograms were visualised with iodine vapour. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used for drying extracts. The analytical samples were routinely dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 *in vacuo* at room temperature. IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs on Perkin-Elmer FT-IR model RX-9. UV spectra were recorded with a Hitachi UV-Vis-NIR model U 3501. NMR spectra were recorded with Bruker AM-300L and Bruker Avance 300 superconducting magnet instruments in CDCl_3 , recording at 300 MHz for ^1H and 75.5 MHz for ^{13}C chemical shifts are reported in δ , ppm; coupling constants in Hz.

The purities of starting materials were verified from comparison of their melting points with those recorded in literature; as well as from their IR and ^1H NMR spectra.

Preparation of the starting materials :

Preparation of nitrones :

The microwave irradiation assisted procedure developed by us⁶ was utilised for the preparation of the *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl nitrones. A BPL Sanyo domestic microwave oven, Model BMO-700T, was used.

Preparation of dipolarophiles :

Benzylideneacetone was prepared by the literature method⁷. The same procedure as for the preparation of benzylideneacetone was used except for substituting benzaldehyde with 4-chlorobenzaldehyde.

General procedure for the cycloaddition reactions :

The reaction of the nitrone (0.0044 mol) with a three-molar excess of the dipolarophile (0.0132 mol) was car-

ried out in refluxing dry thiophene free toluene ($\sim 120^\circ\text{C}$) under argon atmosphere for 10–16 h. Progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC and ^1H NMR spectroscopy at different intervals. ^1H NMR analysis of the crude product, obtained after removal of the solvent in a Büchi rotary evaporator under reduced pressure, showed the presence of only one product (**3**). The product was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina and recrystallized.

*Reaction of C-(4-nitrophenyl)-N-phenyl nitrone (1a) with 4-chloro-benzylideneacetone (2a) : 3,4-trans-4,5-trans-2-phenyl-3-(4'-nitrophenyl)-5-(4''-chlorophenyl)-4-acetyl isoxazolidine (3a), $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$: Reaction time 10 h, conversion 94%; eluted by *n*-hexane : ethyl acetate (2 : 1). It was recrystallised as yellow crystals, m.p. 132°C (petrol-chloroform 4 : 1), isolated yield 1.582 g (85%). Found : C, 65.14; H, 4.50; N, 6.42%; $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 65.33; H, 4.53; N, 6.62%; IR (KBr) $\nu_{\text{max}} \text{cm}^{-1}$: 3073, 2922, 2864, 1710 (C=O), 1518, 1345 (nitro), 1594, 1490, 1251 (aromatic C=C), 1162 (C-Cl), 827 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 750, 693 (mono-substituted benzene ring). For NMR data see Table 1.*

*Reaction of C-(4-chlorophenyl)-N-phenyl nitrone (1b) with benzylideneacetone (2b) : 3,4-trans-4,5-trans-2,5-diphenyl-3-(4'-chlorophenyl)-4-acetyl isoxazolidine (3b), $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}_2\text{Cl}$: Reaction time 12 h, conversion 84%; eluted by *n*-hexane : ethyl acetate (4 : 1). It crystallised as pale brown crystals, m.p. 126°C (petroleum : chloroform 4 : 1), isolated yield 1.247 g (75%). Found : C, 71.98; H, 5.43; N, 3.61%; $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}_2\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 72.11; H, 5.33; N, 3.71%; IR (KBr) $\nu_{\text{max}} \text{cm}^{-1}$: 3051, 2931, 2866, 1712 (C=O), 1593, 1410, 1255 (aromatic C=C), 1162 (C-chloro), 827 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 749, 690 (mono-substituted benzene ring); ^1H NMR : δ 5.07 (d, 7.3; 3-H), 3.61 (dd, 7.3, 9.0; H-4), 5.13 (d, 9.0; H-5), 1.82 (s; CH_3), 6.90–6.99 (m, H-2,6,4/A), 7.16 (t, 7.1; H-3,5/A), 7.22–7.48 (other aromatic protons); ^{13}C NMR : δ 72.81 (C-3), 74.64 (C-4), 82.36 (C-5), 31.12 (CH_3), 203.42 (CO), 150.94 (C-1/A), 114.56 (C-2,6/A), 122.41 (C-4/A), 135.05 (C-1/B), 127.88 (C-2,6/C), 128.09 (C-3,5/B), 133.27 (C-4/B), 139.79 (C-1/C), 129.14 (C-4/C), 129.43, 129.58, 129.87 (other aromatic carbons).*

Reaction of C-phenyl-N-phenyl nitrone (1c) with 4-chloro-benzylideneacetone (2a) : 3,4-trans-4,5-trans-2,3-

diphenyl-5-(4'-chlorophenyl)-4-acetyl isoxazolidine (3c), $C_{23}H_{20}NO_2Cl$: Reaction time 16 h, conversion 80%; eluted by *n*-hexane : ethyl acetate (4 : 1). It recrystallised as pale brown crystals, m.p. 118 °C (petrol : chloroform 1 : 1), isolated yield 1.197 g (72%). Found : C, 71.87; H, 5.43; N, 3.61%; $C_{23}H_{20}NO_2Cl$ requires : C, 72.11; H, 5.33; N, 3.71%; IR (KBr) ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 3032, 2919 (aromatic CH), 1706 (C=O), 1651, 1588, 1405 (aromatic C=C), 1186 (C-chloro), 817 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 752, 693 (mono-substituted benzene ring); 1H NMR : δ 5.04 (d, 7.1; 3-H), 3.67 (dd, 7.1, 9.0; H-4), 5.15 (d, 9.0; H-5), 2.24 (s; CH_3), 6.87–6.94 (H-2,6,4/A), 7.23 (t, 8.6; H-3,5), 7.28–7.53 (9H, other aromatic protons); ^{13}C NMR : δ 73.76 (C-3), 74.64 (C-4), 82.15 (C-5), 27.66 (CH_3), 197.94 (CO), 151.16 (C-1/A), 114.54 (C-2,6/A), 122.32 (C-4/A), 135.49 and 136.39 (C-1/B and C-1/C), 126.49 (C-4/B), 127.46 (C-2,6/C), 132.93 (C-4/C), 128.98, 129.10, 129.18, 129.39 (other aromatic carbons).

Reaction of C-(4-nitrophenyl)-N-phenyl nitron (1a) with benzylideneacetone (2b) : 3,4-trans-4,5-trans-2,5-diphenyl-3-(4'-nitrophenyl)-4-acetyl isoxazolidine (3d), $C_{23}H_{20}N_2O_4$: Reaction time 10 h, conversion 94%; eluted by hexane : ethyl acetate (4 : 2). It crystallised as yellow crystals, m.p. 120 °C (petrol-chloroform 1 : 1), isolated yield 1.435 g (84%). Found : C, 71.00; H, 5.25; N, 7.11%; $C_{23}H_{20}N_2O_4$ requires : C, 71.12; H, 5.19; N, 7.21%; UV λ_{max} (MeOH) : 258 nm ($\log \epsilon = 3.96$), 278 nm (sh, $\log \epsilon = 4.02$); IR (KBr) ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 3072, 2920, 2862, 1709 (C=O), 1517, 1345 (nitro), 1654, 1594, 1489, 1252 (aromatic C=C), 825 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 749, 692 (mono-substituted benzene ring); 1H NMR : δ 5.49 (d, 6.6; 3-H), 3.75 (dd, 6.6, 9.3; H-4), 5.12 (d, 9.3; H-5), 1.90 (s; CH_3), 6.99 (H-2,6,4/A), 7.28 (dt, t-8.0, d-8.7; H-3,5/A), 7.73 (d, 8.7; H-2,6/B), 8.26 (d, 8.7; H-3,5/B), 7.41–7.48 (C-2,6,3,5,4/C); ^{13}C NMR : δ 71.80 (C-3), 74.74 (C-4), 83.66 (C-5), 30.74 (CH_3), 203.00 (CO), 150.75 (C-1/A), 114.12 (C-2,6/A), 122.36 (C-4/A), 149.00 (B-1), 127.30 (C-2,6/C), 124.38 (C-3,5/B), 147.60 (C-4/B), 135.63 (C-1/C), 129.6 (C-4/C), 129.17, 129.27 (other aromatic carbons).

Reaction of C-phenyl-N-phenyl nitron (1c) with benzylideneacetone (2b) : 3,4-trans-4,5-trans-2,3,5-triphenyl-4-acetyl isoxazolidine (3e), $C_{23}H_{21}NO_2$: Reaction time 16 h, total conversion 82%; eluted by *n*-hexane :

ethyl acetate (4 : 1). It crystallized as off-white crystals, m.p. 112 °C (petrol-chloroform 1 : 1), isolated yield 1.097 g (72%). Found : C, 80.24; H, 6.25; N 4.18%; $C_{23}H_{21}NO_2$ requires : C, 80.44; H, 6.16; N, 4.08%; IR (KBr) ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 3032, 2919, 1706 (C=O), 1651, 1588, 1405 (aromatic C=C), 750, 690 (mono-substituted benzene ring); 1H NMR : δ 5.05 (d, 7.0; 3-H), 3.68 (dd, 7.0, 9.3; H-4), 5.12 (d, 9.3; H-5), 1.86 (s; CH_3), 6.99 (H-2,6,4/A), 7.16–7.51 (11H, other aromatic protons); ^{13}C NMR : δ 73.80 (C-3), 74.71 (C-4), 82.66 (C-5), 31.00 (CH_3), 203.42 (CO), 150.95 (C-1/A), 114.32 (C-2,6/A), 129.27/129.17 (C-3,5/A), 122.38 (C-4/A), 149.00 (C-1/B), 127.30 (C-2,6/B), 124.38 (C-3,5/B), 147.60 (C-4/B), 135.63 (C-1/C), 129.27/129.17, 129.60 (other aromatic carbons).

X-Ray crystallographic analysis of (3a) :

Cycloadduct (3a) was recrystallised from petroleum ether-chloroform to obtain single crystals. Diffraction data were recorded on a Bruker Smart Apex II CCD area detector diffractometer operating the Mo $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.212 \text{ \AA}$). Recording was done at 296°(2) K. The structures were solved by direct methods (SHELXS) and refined using isotropic, then anisotropic thermal factors (SHELXL program). The crystallographic parameters of (3a) are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Crystal data and details of (3) for the structure determination

Structure	3
CCDC reference no.	868952
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	P-1
Empirical formula	$C_{23}H_{19}ClN_2O_4$
Mol. wt.	422.85
Parameters (\AA , °)	
<i>a</i> , <i>b</i> , <i>c</i>	9.9219(7), 11.5376(7), 11.6700(7)
α , β , γ	116.913(3), 107.363(3), 99.685(3)
Volume (\AA^3)	1062.30(13)
<i>Z</i>	2
<i>D</i> (calc.) (g/cm^{-3})	1.322
<i>M</i> (Mo $K\alpha$) (mm)	0.212
Temperature (K)	296
Radiation (Angstrom)	Mo $K\alpha$ 0.71073
Refinement	
R, wR2, S	0.0414, 0.1279, 1.04

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